

**D3.1 Handbook for
implementation and
replication of Citizen
Science Labs and
Behavioural Change
Interventions**

WP3, T3.1.

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TECHNICAL REFERENCES

Project Acronym	SPOON
Project Title	Food Systems in transition – ParticipatOry, Open citizen research for sustainable Nutrition
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Project Duration	December 2024 – November 2028 (48 months)

Deliverable No.	D3.1
Dissemination level*	PU
Work Package	WP3 Citizen Science Labs centralise framework, coordination and guidance
Task	T3.1. Creating centralised SPOON CSL framework: preparing CSL methods
Lead beneficiary	Science For Change (SFC)
Contributing beneficiary/ies	Carla Mongolla (EV ILVO); Françoise Beaussant (HBK); Francesca Grossi, Arlind Xhelili (CSCP)
Due date of deliverable	30.11.2025
Actual submission date	30.11.2025

- PU = Public
- SEN= sensitive

CHANGE HISTORY / REVIEW TABLE

v/d	Date	Beneficiary	Author
D1	13/08/2025	SFC shared the first outline for the framework for partner feedback.	Òscar Larraga
D2	17/09/2025	CSCP provided feedback to the outline	Francesca Grossi
D3	29/10/2025	SFC completed a more comprehensive version of the document.	Nora Salas Seoane
D4	11/11/2025	SFC shared a first draft for quality review to EV ILVO and HBK with integrated feedback from CSCP.	Òscar Larraga and Nora Salas Seoane
D5	26/11/2025	SFC integrated the feedback of the reviewers and shared the deliverable draft with the project coordinator for review	Òscar Larraga and Nora Salas Seoane
D6	27/11/2025	CSCP performed the technical check of the document and shared with the deliverable owner for a final review / check.	Arlind Xhelili
V1	28/11/2025	SFC integrated feedback and prepared version 1 (final version) of the deliverable for submission.	Òscar Larraga and Nora Salas Seoane

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ACRONYMS

Acronym	Description
AIT	Austrian Institute of Technology
BCIs	Behavioural Change Interventions
BFL	Bruges Food Lab
CS	Citizen Science
CSCP	Collaborating Centre on Sustainable Consumption and Production
CSLs	Citizen Science Labs
ITC	Innovation Technology Cluster
HBK	Hochschule für Bildende Künste (Braunschweig University of Art)
H&S	Healthy and sustainable food
LL	Living Lab

KEY TERMS

The presented terms are plain language definitions to help readers navigate the document. The interpretation has been tailored and adapted to the SPOON project needs and activities and is aimed primarily as a common reference, without exhaustively capturing the meaning behind the terms. More expansive definitions and descriptions are provided further as necessary.

Term	Basic definition
Methodology framework	A structured approach that defines the principles, methods, and processes guiding how a project or research activity is designed and implemented to ensure coherence, rigor, and reproducibility.
Citizen Science	A collaborative research approach where citizens are engaged and work along professional scientists in different phases of the scientific process.
Living Lab	A participatory environment where communities co-create, test, and evaluate solutions in real-life settings to foster innovation.
Citizen Science Lab	A core participatory mechanism of SPOON, which blends citizen science and living lab methods, where citizens act as both researchers and food system change agents.

Citizen Science Project	The set of activities implemented within SPOON's CSLs to engage citizens in research on food behaviours and co-design the Digital Toolset.
Behaviour Change Intervention	Co-designed and context-specific set of actions in the CSLs regions that aim to experiment, learn, and shift individual or collective food consumption behaviours.
SPOON Digital Toolset	A GDPR-compliant suite of tools, including a questionnaire app, personal data wallet, data-sharing platform, and APIs, that enables people to collect, manage, and share their food-related data securely and transparently.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 SPOON

According to recent research, food systems are responsible for up to 37% of the global greenhouse gas emissions (Crippa et al., 2021) and if the trend is to continue their climate impact can surge to 50–90% (Oakden et al., 2021). Conflicts, climate shocks, and widening inequalities have weakened global food supply chains. Despite abundant food in affluent nations, income inequality results in significant food insecurity - **in Europe alone about 38 million people lack access to sufficient, healthy food** (IFOAM, n.d.). Addressing these interconnected issues requires **multi-level knowledge, innovative technologies, behavioural shifts, and transformative policies that consider cultural practices influencing dietary habits.**

Traditional top-down approaches to food system challenges are insufficient in today's rapidly changing landscape. The **SPOON project proposes a paradigm shift by placing citizens' local realities and operational settings at the forefront of transformation through citizen science.** The latter can be placed as a powerful tool in empowering communities to contribute to knowledge generation and fostering collaboration for a more inclusive and sustainable food system. By understanding the interplay between citizen science, consumer behaviours, and data sharing, SPOON aims to enhance context-specific, cross-sector and data-driven decision-making for healthier, more sustainable diets and reduced food insecurity.

In **SPOON, citizens will actively participate in the research process and use innovative digital tools to collect, analyse, and interpret food data.** Accordingly, in view of the background and objectives above, the project will seek to:

- **Develop an analytical framework and increase understanding of factors influencing healthy and sustainable food consumption.**
- **Implement Citizen Science Labs (CSLs) and Behaviour Change Interventions (BCI)** with citizens and food stakeholders to collect, visualise and interpret data on consumers' consumption behaviours and their local food purchasing and consumption environments
- **Co-create and deploy the SPOON digital toolset** that includes a multimedia questionnaire generator and a personal data wallet to enable data collection and analysis (citizen science)
- **Establish a GDPR-compliant data governance framework** focusing on privacy, data sharing, and inter-operability
- **Produce guidelines and a capacity-building programme for citizen science and consumer behaviour change projects** aiming to exploit, replicate and accelerate project learnings, insights and results
- **Draft policy recommendations** to enhance data-driven policies through better use of citizen data, digital tools, and cross-sector collaboration.

Through its initiatives—especially key components like the CSLs, BCI, and the citizen science digital toolset—the project will address several critical topics. It will investigate food waste by identifying the types of food most frequently discarded, the underlying causes, and strategies to reduce waste. Another focus will be the design of food environments and their influence on

consumer behaviour and food choices. The project will also explore food insecurity, examining factors that affect access to sustainable, healthy food for vulnerable communities and the mechanisms driving these disparities. Additionally, it will assess transparency and accountability across the food supply chain, from production to consumption, and their impact on purchasing and eating behaviours. Finally, it will analyse how demographic factors shape sustainable food consumption patterns and behaviours.

SPOON has selected **six European locations as its project target regions—Germany, Greece, Italy, Belgium, Spain, and Slovenia**—that reflect diverse local contexts, geographical representation, varying climate conditions and sustainability challenges. The selection also considered differences in local food production systems and accessibility to healthy and sustainable food, alongside the presence of food deserts or food swamps, where access to nutritious food is limited or unbalanced. Additionally, levels of food insecurity and the variety of thematic challenges faced by each location were key factors in the decision-making process. By empowering citizens and engaging food stakeholders across the supply chain, SPOON aims to spark a collective journey towards a more just, sustainable, and resilient food future for all.

The **SPOON project is funded under the European Union’s Horizon Europe programme and will run for 4 years (2024-2028)**. It brings together a consortium of 16 European partners. The Collaborating Centre on Sustainable Consumption and Production (CSCP) a think and do tank based in Wuppertal, Germany acts as the project coordinator.

1.2 HANDBOOK'S OBJECTIVE

The objective of this Handbook is to provide an overview of the main actions and activities CSLs will perform in their regions to transform food systems into healthier and sustainable communities. The document first presents the 1) SPOON Foundational Components for a Centralised Methodological Framework, explaining the combination of methodologies that end up forming the SPOON one, combining aspects of Citizen Science and Living Lab methodologies adapted to the SPOON objectives. Second, the document presents a 2) description of the 6 CSLs describing its key topics in each region, existing initiatives, main methodological challenges, and the strategies proposed to address them. 3) The SPOON methodological framework in action is provided in the third section, working as a guideline for the implementation of the Citizen Science project in each CSL. The fourth section is devoted to 4) Stakeholder mapping, recruitment and engagement strategies that are crucial for the development of the citizen science projects, followed by the 5) Competencies, roles and responsibilities amongst project partners to deploy the described activities (Table 1).

Table 1: Content of the report

	Description
1 - SPOON: Foundational components of a centralised methodological framework	This first section introduces the foundations of the two main methodological dimensions underpinning the project and explains how they interconnect, while contextualising the importance of Behavioural Change Interventions within the project framework.

2 - The 6 CSLs in SPOON	It presents the six CSLs across the project's six regions Germany, Greece, Italy, Belgium, Spain, and Slovenia with its objectives, already developed initiatives, characteristics and expected outcomes.
3 - The SPOON methodological framework action	This section constitutes the core of the report. It systematically describes the structure of the SPOON methodology, including the number and objectives of the workshops to be held, the expected number of participants, the approximate timeline, and the anticipated outputs. The methodology is framed and justified in relation to its content, its structural elements, and its alignment with the Digital Toolset.
4 - Stakeholder mapping, recruitment and engagement strategies	This section addresses the actions regarding stakeholder mapping, recruitment and engagement for the implementation of the CSLs— including actions directed to consumers and stakeholders.
5) Competences, roles and responsibilities	The final section defines the roles and responsibilities of all profiles involved in the implementation of the CSLs. At the first level, it outlines the role of the direct implementers; and, at the second level, it clarifies the contribution of the WP leaders to the implementation process.

2 SPOON: FOUNDATIONAL COMPONENTS OF A CENTRALISED METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 CITIZEN SCIENCE

2.1.1 A definition

The term **Citizen Science (CS)** was first published in 1989 within the MIT Technology Review presenting community laboratories to study environmental problems (Kerson, 1989). However, the public participation in research has a long history, with the public participating within natural history, astronomy and archaeology, amongst other fields of knowledge. In 2014, the Oxford English Dictionary included the term CS, defining it broadly enough to encompass all scientific disciplines: **“Scientific work undertaken by members of the general public, often in collaboration with or under the direction of professional scientists and scientific institutions”** (Oxford University Press, 2014). CS is science, and as such, it reflects the same multiplicity of purposes, methodologies, and designs as traditional science, including reliable data, peer review and scientific scrutiny (Lepczyk et al, 2020). In the European context, CS is understood as a broad concept part of the Open Science Agenda, encompassing various levels of citizen involvement in scientific research. Citizens may participate as mere data collectors or collaborators, or engage more actively as co-designers of the research processes (European Commission, 2013). In that sense, we refer to citizens participating in science as *citizen scientists*. The European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) goes one step beyond in defining that **“CS projects actively involve citizens in scientific endeavour that generates new knowledge or understanding”** - adding citizen scientists an agency as active contributors to the scientific process of knowledge production (ECSA, 2025). Individuals who merely participate in studies as research subjects, such as those enrolled in clinical trials or social surveys, are not considered citizen scientists.

2.1.2 Levels of participation

There are different levels of participation within CS. The spectrum between conventional science and *Extreme CS* is directly linked to the diversity of participant profiles and the degree in which they are involved within the scientific process - as shown **Figure 1**. In classic science, the research is carried out exclusively by professional scientists with high formal education leading all stages of the process. In contrast, *Extreme CS* refers to situated, bottom-up practices that consider local needs, customs, and cultures, engaging broad networks of people in different stages of the scientific process to co-design and develop both new tools and knowledge-generation processes aimed at fostering positive transformations in the world. The SPOON CSLs design foresees a broad and inclusive participation of citizens that moves beyond extractive models of data collection considering co-creation practices amongst several phases of the process. As such, SPOON positions itself between Level 3 and 4 of participation and engagement of the participation ladder, corresponding to the *Participatory CS* and the *Extreme CS*.

Figure 1: Levels of involvement in CS

2.1.3 Data collection protocols and participants' engagement

CS projects have two main dimensions: the **scientific** one (ensuring the rigor of the data) and the **social/educational** one (raising awareness, training, and building community). These two dimensions are closely linked to **engagement**: the social dimension depends on the participants' commitment to carrying out the activities, while the scientific content of the project is what initially attracts or discourages individuals from participating. In this regard, it is essential that data collection and analysis protocols are designed not only to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the data but also to maintain participants' interest and enjoyment, encouraging their sustained engagement throughout the project. These protocols often need to be simplified, given that citizen scientists do not necessarily have the same skills or resources as professional scientists.

Regarding **engagement strategies**, to achieve long-term commitment, CS projects often rely on various mechanisms to make participation more appealing. Examples include:

- **Gamification**: Transforming the data collection process into a game-like experience to enhance motivation, engagement, and sustained participation.
- **Sense of progress**: Structuring participation into stages, giving participants a sense of advancement.
- **Distribution of roles**: Assigning different roles within the group to foster teamwork and strengthen participation.
- **Creating a community**: Building a sense of belonging encourages participants to remain active and fosters a moral commitment to contribute to the collective good.
- **Non-monetary incentives**: As participants are volunteers, financial rewards are generally not possible. However, small non-monetary tokens of appreciation, such as gifts, can be an appropriate and feasible way to acknowledge contributions in certain cases.

All these strategies can be combined and integrated into the data collection protocol to make the project more interesting, feasible, and attractive for participants, with the aim of ensuring long-term engagement. SPOON adheres to CS as a discipline that play a broader scientific and societal role. CS contributes to making science more inclusive, democratic, and socially robust, while also enhancing its capacity to address complex, emerging challenges that are difficult to grasp through narrowly defined disciplinary approaches. CS holds also a strong potential for improving relevant European policies. SPOON is designed to fully harness the potential of CS, while also addressing its methodological limitations and associated risks.

2.1.4 The 10 principles of Citizen Science

As CS has matured over the last decade, shared best practices have emerged. In 2015, the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) formalized these by developing the "Ten Principles of Citizen Science." Based on the collective experience of ECSA members, these principles outline the fundamentals of good practice in CS, applicable across all scientific disciplines and cultural contexts. These are the 10 principles of CS as written by ECSA:

1. **CS projects actively involve citizens in scientific endeavour that generates new knowledge or understanding.** Citizens may act as contributors, collaborators, or as project leader and have a meaningful role in the project.
2. **CS projects have a genuine science outcome.** *For example, answering a research question or informing conservation action, management decisions or environmental policy.*
3. **Both the professional scientists and the citizen scientists benefit from taking part.** *Benefits may include the publication of research outputs, learning opportunities, personal enjoyment, social benefits, satisfaction through contributing to scientific evidence e.g. to address local, national and international issues, and through that, the potential to influence policy.*
4. **Citizen scientists may, if they wish, participate in multiple stages of the scientific process.** *This may include developing the research question, designing the method, gathering and analysing data, and communicating the results.*
5. **Citizen scientists receive feedback from the project.** *For example, how their data are being used and what the research, policy or societal outcomes are.*
6. **CS is considered a research approach like any other, with limitations and biases that should be considered and controlled for.** *However, unlike traditional research approaches, CS provides opportunity for greater public engagement and democratisation of science.*
7. **CS project data and meta-data are made publicly available and where possible, results are published in an open access format.** *Data sharing may occur during or after the project, unless there are security or privacy concerns that prevent this.*
8. **Citizen scientists are acknowledged in project results and publications.**
9. **CS programs are evaluated for their scientific output, data quality, participant experience and wider societal or policy impact.**
10. **The leaders of CS projects take into consideration legal and ethical issues surrounding copyright, intellectual property, data sharing agreements, confidentiality, attribution, and the environmental impact of any activities.**

Within the development of the SPOON's methodological framework, the 10 Principles of CS have been carefully integrated to ensure alignment with the science of CS, scientific rigour, uphold ethical standards, and foster a meaningful and positive experience for all participants involved. In the next section, the living labs methodology is presented, also as part of the SPOON methodological framework.

2.2 LIVING LABS

2.2.1 A definition

According to the European Commission (2009), a **Living Lab (LL)** is defined as **“a user-driven open innovation ecosystem based on a business-citizens-government partnership which enables users to take active part in the research, development and innovation process”**

In a similar vein, the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) describes LLs as **“user-centred open innovation ecosystems based on a systematic user co-creation approach, integrating research and innovation processes in real-life communities and settings.”** (Paskaleva & Cooper, 2021). Both definitions highlight three core components that characterise the Living Lab approach: a user-centred perspective, the pursuit of research and innovation, and a collaborative multi-actor environment. The definition underpins the idea that involving citizens as key actors in the design and innovation process leads to products and services that better respond to real needs, thereby increasing both economic and social sustainability. However, the concept remains intentionally open and adaptable, allowing LLs to take different forms—whether as physical or digital experimentation spaces, participatory methodologies, or systemic frameworks designed to foster innovation in real-world contexts. Above all, they serve as systemic research tools focused on generating territorial impact⁸. As interdisciplinary and context-driven systems, LLs operate through collaborative methodologies that bring together diverse stakeholders in a shared environment. This system is built around four key components:

- **Context:** the real-life environment to be studied and impacted.
- **Objective:** the innovation-driven goal aimed at generating knowledge and change.
- **Participants:** the actors who contribute ideas, perspectives, and governance to co-create and test solutions.
- **Methodology:** a set of collaborative and iterative activities that support innovation processes.

2.2.2 The context: a real-life environment

LLs are open innovation environments that operate in **real-life settings**. Their method involves **active stakeholder participation to co-design, test, and validate** new products or services directly within their actual social, geographical, and cultural context. This approach allows them to integrate diverse **contextual and experiential knowledge**—which is often inaccessible in a conventional lab—to create meaningful, locally relevant, and sustainable solutions (Hossain et al., 2019).

2.2.3 Goals and outcomes

LLs aim to develop, test, and refine innovative solutions within **real-life settings** through **active stakeholder participation**.

Their core goals are threefold:

1. **To co-create value** by engaging diverse actors (users, institutions, companies).
2. **To ensure solutions are relevant** and replicable by testing them in real-world contexts.
3. **To contribute to sustainability** by addressing systemic challenges (Aquilué et al., 2021).

To achieve this, LLs combine co-creation with a strong focus on **continuous impact evaluation**, which is essential for assessing both intended and unintended effects. The results of a LL are categorized as **tangible outcomes** (like prototypes, services, or products) and **intangible outcomes** (such as new know-how, concepts, or methodologies), which are often hybrid. This capacity to link participatory innovation with evidence-based assessment allows LLs to deliver actionable, locally-grounded, and meaningful change⁹.

2.2.4 Participants

LLs are built on **structured collaboration** among diverse actors, often described as the "quadruple helix model" (public sector, private sector, civil society, and academia). A key feature is the **early engagement** of all stakeholders affected by the innovation. This inclusive approach ensures diverse perspectives are integrated, allowing the group to collectively identify challenges and co-develop solutions that are better aligned with local realities. This process leads to more legitimate, feasible, and robust outcomes, making collaboration the very **foundation** of the methodology, not just an add-on (Fuglsang, 2021).

2.2.5 Methodologies

LL methodologies are built on the twin pillars of **user engagement** and **co-creation**, both of which are grounded in **real-life experimentation** and accompanied by **continuous evaluation**⁹. The process is **non-linear and iterative**, involving users actively from the initial ideation phase. This approach rejects the idea of users as passive subjects, instead treating them as **co-creators** and "experts in their daily lives" by valuing their experiential knowledge (García Robles et al., 2015). Rather than being fixed, the methodology is **fluid, experimental, and context-sensitive**, often adapting methods like **design thinking** and **participatory design**. The **core principle of co-creation** fosters shared ownership through a trust-based process. This requires the **equal recognition of all knowledge types**—whether scientific, professional, or experiential—to ensure the resulting innovations are resilient, valuable to all stakeholders, and locally grounded (Mortensen et al., 2023). Design approaches—such as human-centred design, participatory design, and design thinking—are commonly used, alongside ethnographic methods and lead user innovation. These are adapted to local contexts and facilitated by professionals to capture unstructured yet valuable input. Participants often use visual tools like sketches or models to express solutions. Crucially, LLs provide spaces that enable playful and experimental approaches to public sector innovation.

2.3 THE COMBINATION OF CITIZEN SCIENCE AND LIVING LABS

SPOON adopts an innovative approach by combining LLs and CS methodologies through the creation of CSLs, which aim to ensure and enable citizens' involvement in shaping our socio-economic and political frameworks through co-creation and data collection. This methodological approach functions as a framework for engaging citizens and stakeholders throughout the research process, helping to increase the transparency, credibility, and legitimacy of solutions that may impact citizens' lives.

On the one hand, as a key element of **CS**, the project **involves non-professional individuals in an inclusive way not only in the collection and interpretation of data, but also in the co-design of the research tools and the research questions**, with the objective of generating scientific knowledge on how regional food systems impact the everyday habits and routines of citizens. This approach aligns with the ECSA principles and the Extreme CS Model presented above.

On the other hand, this knowledge-generation process—based on collaboration between professionals and non-professionals—is combined with key features of the LL methodology. Firstly, the involvement of actors from various sectors of society—namely the public sector, private sector, academia, and civil society—as well as the inclusion of diverse consumer

profiles and food system stakeholders, ensures a **broad spectrum of perspectives that can converge to develop holistic and cross-cutting solutions**. Secondly, the use of **co-design and co-creation methods places creativity at the core and allows for the exploration of new resources, procedures, and food chains**. Thirdly, **the six regions act as real-life environments** where the proposed solutions are tested following earlier co-creation processes. Finally, **multiple iterations** allow for the continuous improvement of the methodology throughout the project, including the adjustment of procedures and tested solutions to better fit each regional context.

The integration of these two complementary approaches establishes a coherent methodological framework composed of two core components. Each pilot—conceived as the set of activities implemented in each region to promote behavioural shifts towards healthier and more sustainable food practices—will comprise an initial phase involving the co-created design of research tools, as well as the collection and interpretation of data, referred to as the Citizen Science Project. This will be followed by the deployment of the Behavioural Change Interventions (BCIs).

2.3.1 The Citizen Science Project

The Citizen Science Project (CSP) refers to the **set of activities carried out with citizens within the CSLs to gather insights into two main aspects**. First, it seeks to **understand the eating habits of the population in each region**. Second, it **collects feedback on the usability of the various features of the Digital Toolset**.

During this stage, CS and LL methodologies are applied to gather and interpret the knowledge required to understand each region's food system and the behaviours associated with healthy and sustainable food practices. The aim is not only to collect data, but also to analyse it collaboratively with citizen scientists to generate relevant insights that will inform the design of the Behavioural Change Interventions.

Given that SPOON follows an Extreme CS approach, participants contribute to both data collection and the development of the tools used during the process. In the collaborative workshops, they take part in shaping the Digital Toolset, including its functionalities, navigation, and overall usability. A **key element of this co-design process is the digital questionnaire**, which will serve as a core research instrument for gathering information on food habits. The involvement of participants ensures that the questionnaire is adapted to local specificities and cultural contexts, while also supporting broader outreach and more diverse data collection. **To complement the questionnaire, the Food Journal is introduced as an optional ethnographic activity that encourages participants to reflect more deeply on their dietary practices over time**. Together, these tools enable the project to gather extensive information, which will be examined both through inductive analysis and participatory sessions where results are jointly interpreted.

Despite the participation of both stakeholders and consumers in this phase of the project, the CSP is primarily focused on consumers, whose behaviour will be studied through the food cycle narrative and CS methodologies. Nonetheless, it is essential to highlight that stakeholders also have a crucial role at the end of this project phase. They will work **jointly with consumers to collectively analyse the data and insights gathered throughout the CSP in order to co-design a research question for the next phase, as well as to define and examine the foundations upon which the BCIs will be developed**.

2.3.2 The Behaviour Change Interventions

Once all data have been collected and a solid knowledge base has been generated through both collective interpretation and quantitative and qualitative analysis, the conceptualisation of the BCIs will take place. In the context of SPOON, **BCIs are defined as actions or processes through which the project actively intervenes in a specific situation within the food system, with the aim of modifying or guiding user behaviour towards healthier and more sustainable food practices.** This intervention is deliberate, well-considered, structured, consensual, and strategic, pursuing a clearly defined objective.

The design of the BCIs will draw on the knowledge generated during the CSP in each CSL individually, in combination with the desk research on best practices for system interventions. The conceptualisation of the BCIs will involve food system actors and stakeholders from food-related sectors identified during the CSP. This participatory process will ensure that the BCIs are tailored to the specific context and needs of each region. The design of the BCIs will thus result from a co-design process that integrates diverse perspectives.

Once the BCIs for each CSL have been designed, implementation will follow. This phase will be supervised by the Collaborating Centre on Sustainable Consumption and Production (CSCP) and will involve applying the defined actions or processes in each territory with the active participation of food system actors. The main objective will be to evaluate the impact of the intervention on people's behaviour—whether or not it changes, to what extent, and with what degree of sustainability—a task that will be undertaken by the Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT).

3 THE 6 CSLs IN SPOON

SPOON has selected **six diverse locations across 6 European countries (Germany, Greece, Italy, Belgium, Spain and Slovenia)**, each representing distinct local contexts and sustainability challenges in relation to food system transformation. The selection was guided by several criteria:

1. **Geographical diversity**—including Western, Eastern, and Southern Europe—and varying climate conditions.
2. **Differences in local food production systems and access to healthy and sustainable food.**
3. **The presence of food deserts and/or food swamps.**
4. **Varying levels of food insecurity.**
5. **Diversity of local thematic challenges.**

What follows in **Table 2** is a brief overview of each region, including general contextual information, the main food-related challenges identified, and the specific objectives and topics that each CSL aims to address throughout the SPOON project.

The six CSLs of the SPOON project are **geographically diverse, representing a broad range of regional contexts across Europe**. Three of them are located in Mediterranean cities, linked to the Mediterranean diet and culinary heritage (Italy, Greece and Spain), while the others are situated in northern or central Europe (Belgium, Germany and Slovenia). Similarly, some CSLs are embedded in highly urban environments—such as Bruges or Thessaloniki—while others are part of more rural ecosystems, like the Pomurje Region, or are adjacent to extensive croplands, as in the case of Valencia. These latter regions contrast with those more reliant on external supply chains, as they are rooted in strong agricultural traditions and produce a significant share of local food.

Despite this diversity, **all CSLs face shared food-related challenges**. On one side, both Braunschweig and Bruges experience a predominance of **unhealthy food options** and a **limited public understanding of what constitutes sustainable and healthy food**. This general lack of awareness is widespread across many European regions, which reinforces the importance of addressing this issue throughout the SPOON project. On the other side, **affordability of healthy food** is identified as a key barrier in Braunschweig—particularly for the middle class—and in the Pomurje Region, where rural poverty, lack of trust, and regional disparities compound the problem.

Valencia, Turin, and Thessaloniki emphasise **pronounced socioeconomic inequalities that hinder access to healthy food**, especially among low-income households, perpetuating the structural nature of food insecurity. Meanwhile, Braunschweig, Bruges, and Pomurje demonstrate that even in more economically developed areas, **cultural and behavioural barriers—such as the dominance of fast food and low food literacy**—continue to obstruct transitions towards healthier and more sustainable food systems. Additionally, food waste emerges as a cross-cutting challenge in Turin, Thessaloniki, and Braunschweig, often linked to expiry date misconceptions and regulatory barriers. These issues underscore the relevance of bio circular strategies in addressing waste throughout the food system.

Although the CSLs share similar challenges, each has chosen to prioritise specific thematic focuses.

- **Braunschweig** focuses on reducing food waste.
- **Thessaloniki** seeks to apply circular economy principles to re-design food behaviours and reduce food waste.
- **Turin** works to expand and improve food aid services with a focus on sustainability and inclusiveness.
- **Bruges** is targeting a behavioural shift away from unhealthy consumption patterns by empowering citizens to make informed food choices.
- **Valencia** prioritises the equitable access to healthy and sustainable food, through evidence-informed policymaking.
- and the **Pomurje region** tackles consumer awareness of sustainability indicators by enabling a better product traceability.

Based on these challenges and thematic priorities, **some CSLs aim to reach a broad audience, reflecting the diversity of their territories, while others —particularly those focusing on food insecurity— target vulnerable groups specifically. Bruges, Thessaloniki, Braunschweig, and Pomurje** fall into the first category, aiming for **broad citizen engagement**. In contrast, **Valencia and Turin are more focused on working with socially and economically fragile populations**. Geographically, although all CSLs aim to address issues at the city level, some, such as Thessaloniki and Turin, are concentrating their efforts in specific neighbourhoods.

In terms of experience, the CSLs display significant variation. The Pomurje CSL, coordinated by the Innovation Technology Cluster (ITC), operates within a well-established LL and boasts the most robust infrastructure and an extensive network of over 100 stakeholders. Braunschweig and Bruges, while rich in experience organising events and artistic outreach, have limited experience in facilitating co-design sessions or implementing CS methodologies. Nevertheless, the Bruges Food Lab (BFL) leads the city's sustainable food strategy and maintains strong connections with local food stakeholders. Thessaloniki and Turin benefit from strong local networks: INCOMMON brings prior participatory experience in Thessaloniki, and Rete delle Case del Quartiere (RETE CdQ) in Turin provides infrastructure, human resources, and a solid background in social innovation. However, both CSLs will require support in engagement strategy and co-design facilitation. Valencia, although new to CS, contributes prior experience in participatory research and has developed digital tools focused on vulnerable groups, such as an app addressing childhood obesity.

Despite their differences, **all six CSLs share a strong commitment to engaging citizens in reshaping local food systems and addressing food insecurity through evidence-based approaches, creativity, and collaboration.** Together, they reflect the broader ambition of the SPOON project to contribute to a more sustainable, healthy, and inclusive food future across Europe.

Table 2: Comparison of the 6 CSLs

	Braunschweig (Germany)	Thessaloniki (Greece)	Turin (Italy)	Bruges (Belgium)	Valencia (Spain)	Pomurje region (Slovenia)
Coordinators and roles	Hochschule für Bildende Künste (HBK) - Braunschweig University of Art: lead and implementation	INCOMMON NON-PROFIT CIVIL LAW COMPANY (INCOMMON): lead and DIMOS THESSALONIKIS (MoThess): implementation	City of Turin (CITTA DI TORINO): lead Rete delle Case del Quartiere (RETE CdQ): implementation	Bruges Food Lab (BFL): lead and implementation	Valencia Innovation Capital (VIC): lead and implementation	Innovation Technology Cluster (ITC) - manager of Green Point Living Lab: lead and implementation
Context	Peri-urban areas with arable land. Strong agricultural tradition (regional shops, vending machines).	Ano Poli, the old town of Thessaloniki. Multicultural cuisine (UNESCO City of Gastronomy).	Rich food tradition; metro-area production. Municipal support (circular economy, short chains).	"Food swamps" (abundance of unhealthy food). Conservative and change-resistant communities.	Rich local food culture ("la Huerta" heritage). Health and sustainable food available.	Most agricultural region in the country. Rural-urban divide.
Thematic focus and main objectives for the BCIs	Waste reduction. Enhance local food access. Explore education for sustainability.	Apply circular economy principles. Identify drivers of food waste to reduce it.	Improve food aid services in an inclusive manner. Understand community needs.	Increase consumer capacity to change from a "food swamp model" to H&S food.	Access to food. Waste reduction. Foster short value chains. Generate evidence-based public policies.	Access to affordable, low-impact food. Understand consumer perception of sustainability indicators.

						Boost healthy and sustainable practices and traceability.
Main challenges	High prices limit access (lower-middle class). Consumer-producer knowledge gap.	Shift to processed foods. Inequitable access (low-income areas). Food waste. Struggles for small farmers.	Access difficulties for vulnerable groups. Stringent regulations drive food waste. Social stigma associated with food.	Lack of healthy and sustainable food available. Consumer-producer disconnection. Inaccessible academic knowledge.	Low local consumption. Limited access (high prices). Rising overweight/obesity (vulnerable groups).	Socio-economic barriers. Lack of healthy and sustainable awareness. Producers lack consumer preference knowledge.
Preferred target groups	Wide range of citizens. People with low healthy and sustainable food awareness. Students.	Wide range of citizens. Specific focus on the Old Town neighbourhood.	Socially or economically fragile groups. Specific focus on the Aurora neighbourhood.	Wide range of citizens.	Vulnerable people experiencing food insecurity. Users of social services.	Wide range of citizens.
Networks	Network of local initiatives (Bahnstadt, Haus der Wissenschaft, Ernährungsrat)	INCOMMON is linked to grassroots actors. MoThess is linked to the city Food Council.	The City of Turin has access to many food stakeholders. Fusilli project: 15 people group who work in food every week.	BFL works as a network of H&S food actors. They are governing the food transition of the city.	BFL has a massive network of public and private entities.	Green Point Living Lab" (ENoLL registered) Green Point Short Food Supply Chain Digital Innovation Hub

<p>Experience and support needed</p>	<p>In need of support for facilitating, performing engagement and Recruitment Strategies and for designing co-creation sessions.</p>	<p>Experienced in workshops implementation and citizens' engagement.</p>	<p>In need of more human resources. In need of support on engagement and facilitation.</p>	<p>Experienced in conducting projects with vulnerable groups. In need of more human resources and of support regarding the LL methodology implementation.</p>	<p>Experienced in LLs methodologies, engagement strategies regarding stakeholders. BFL has not engaged with consumers yet.</p>	<p>Experienced in LLs methodologies.</p>
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4 FROM THEORY TO ACTION

4.1 RATIONALE OF THE FRAMEWORK

This section outlines the rationale behind the development of a centralised methodological framework that fulfils the requirements previously mentioned on the mandatory aspects and features that define CS and LL, while allows to create a common structure and configuration, but respecting the different particularities, interests, needs and differences of the different CSLs.

In order to compile all this information and organize it in a sensible framework, several aspects have been considered to articulate a methodology framework to address the CSP:

- **The content and structure**, regarding the different insights, approaches and narrative that will be addressed.
- **The target audiences and their purpose**, since the project offers different levels of engagement.
- **The alignment with the Digital Toolset**, due to the fact that the Digital Toolset is a significant piece in the articulation of the CSLs' activities implementation.
- **The Food Journal**, as an engagement strategy linked to the project's content and designed to foster a deeper understanding of consumers' behaviour regarding healthy and sustainable food.

It is important to note that the methodological framework covers exclusively the activities carried out within the CSP and, as such, aims to conceive the central CS initiatives, which will serve as a preparatory stage for establishing the foundations required to design, implement, and evaluate the BCIs.

4.1.1 Content and structure

Given that the CSP pursues two distinct objectives, the planned actions will be developed along two main axes. Firstly, the CSP aims to generate datasets on healthy and sustainable food systems through the six CSLs. These datasets will inform the co-design of a questionnaire that will serve as the foundation for the development of the Behavioural Change Interventions. Secondly, the CSP seeks to co-design the functionalities of the Digital Toolset, which will enable the collection of additional data and facilitate user interaction throughout the project.

In light of this dual structure, each project iteration will include two core activities:

- **A workshop dedicated to co-designing a questionnaire** that explores consumers' food habits across the five stages of the food journey: planning, buying, storing, preparing and eating, and disposing.
- **A workshop focused on co-designing the functionalities of the Digital Toolset**, specifically the Dashboard, DataU, DataWallet, and the questionnaire.

Regarding the first activity, which focuses on food-related behaviours, the following topics will be addressed throughout the different iterations:

- **Perceptions, motivations, and behavioural drivers of participants:** Based on the COM-B model and the food environment framework, which assumes that *capability*, *opportunity*, and *motivation* are the three essential components required to influence behavioural change these three dimensions will be explored during the collaborative workshops.
- **Cognitive and social influences affecting food behaviour:** social norms, education, communication, and exposure to information, as well as the symbolic and relational dimensions, need to be addressed to understand how they shape individual choices within their social environments.
- **Connections with relevant food system stakeholders:** producers, retailers, and other related sectors, in order to understand their interactions and behaviours within different segments of the food value chain.

As for the second activity, focused on the co-design of the Digital Toolset, the workshops conducted across the various iterations will address the following aspects:

- **The DataU and DataWallet:** exploring questions of data privacy and participants' willingness, or reluctance, to share personal information.
- **The Questionnaire:** focusing on usability, user experience, and mechanisms for effective data input.
- **The Dashboard:** introducing it as the main user interface for data visualisation and interaction.
- **The SPOON Data Lake (or its equivalent):** discussing its function as a repository for data representation and access. This functionality will only be addressed if it is considered coherent and necessary to test with consumers. Otherwise, it will not be applied in any iteration of the CSP.

All these activities will be structured into a five-iteration process that follows the consumer food cycle narrative and guides the implementation of the CSLs, forming a coherent and iterative process aligned with both objectives.

The three central iterations will constitute the core of the process, while the first iteration will serve as an introductory phase and the final iteration will close the CSP, acting as a launching point for the next stage of the project: the definition of the BCIs.

Accordingly, the structure will be as follows:

- **Iteration 1: The Pre-Pilot.** Initial CSL meetings will be conducted to introduce the SPOON project and the concept of the CSLs to participants. This first action will also validate previous research on food consumption behaviour and data privacy, as well as gather initial impressions and expectations regarding healthy and sustainable food systems to effectively inform the following stages of the methodology.
- **Iteration 2: Planning and purchasing.** Exploration of behaviours related to food planning and purchasing.
- **Iteration 3: Storing, preparing, and eating:** Examination of behavioural patterns related to food storage, preparation, and consumption, particularly concerning sustainability, health, and resource efficiency.

- **Iteration 4: Leftovers and waste management:** Focus on behaviours related to managing leftovers, food storage, and disposal, including circular practices and attitudes towards food waste.
- **Iteration 5: BCIs and return of knowledge:** Interpretation of the data collected throughout the CSP and co-design of the BCIs and related research questions for their assessment.

4.1.2 Target audience and purpose

Participants are broadly divided into two main categories: **consumers** and **stakeholders**.

Regarding consumers, they are the main actors of the CSP, as this stage is designed for citizen scientists to engage from the consumer's perspective, analysing the food cycle through their own experiences.

However, the way consumers participate in the CSP, as well as their level of engagement, can take two different forms:

- **Participation in workshops:** Participants attending the workshops will contribute data on their eating habits and their social context related to food, in order to co-design a set of questions that will allow the collection of more extensive data through the Digital Toolset questionnaire. Additionally, these participants will provide feedback on the functionality of the Digital Toolset and their user experience, helping refine and improve the tool.
- **Interaction with the Digital Tool:** To expand the volume of data collected, the project foresees that the questionnaire co-designed by participants will be published and made accessible through the Digital Toolset. Through the dissemination of this tool, a larger number of citizens will be able to respond to the co-designed questionnaires, enabling the project to gather more comprehensive data and ultimately generate more robust and meaningful results that will serve as the foundation for the design of the BCIs.

Given that most CSLs aim to recruit volunteers who represent the full diversity of profiles within their regions, it is considered necessary—both to harmonise the methodology and to enable meaningful cross-analysis across CSLs—that **all CSLs ensure participant diversity across key sociodemographic characteristics**. Therefore, it is required that participants include individuals from different age groups, genders, income levels, educational backgrounds, household compositions, and geographical origins. Since the intersection of these characteristics creates a wide variety of profiles that cannot be fully represented within a single workshop, **a minimum set of indicators has been established to guide recruitment based on specific sociodemographic traits**. As such, each CSL will be expected to include participants who meet certain defined criteria.

Table 3: Main criteria to ensure diversity.

	Criteria	Categories
Gender	Ensure an approximately 50% distribution between men and women, and make an effort to include	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Woman • Man • Non-binary

	participants situated across the gender spectrum, such as non-binary, trans, or other gender-diverse individuals.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other
Age	Guarantee a minimum of two participants per age group, organised in 10-year intervals.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 18-29 years' old • 30-39 years' old • 40-49 years' old • 50-59 years' old • 60-69 years' old • 70 years old or more
Income level	Secure a minimum of three participants for each income level.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low income (below average) • Medium income (around average) • High income (above average)
Educational level	Secure around two participants for each educational level.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No formal education • Compulsory education • Higher education • Postgraduate education
Area of the city	Strive to avoid a concentration of participants residing in only a few specific areas of the city.	Each CSL should establish their own categories depending on their local context.
Geographical origin	Ensure at least two participants who identify with each category.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local-born • National migrants • International migrants from High-Income countries • International migrants from Low-Income countries
Household composition	Ensure at least one participant who identifies with each type of household composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Single-person household • Couple without children • Couple with children • Single-parent household • Extended or multi-generational household • Shared household (roommates / cohabiting adults)

It requires a proactive effort to reach and include some of these groups, as they are often the most difficult to engage in initiatives of this kind. **In line with SPOON's commitment to inclusiveness, ensuring the participation of underrepresented populations in the workshop participant pool is a key priority.** However, it should be noted that the table serves merely as a source of inspiration and a reference framework for developing recruitment strategies, and should not be understood as a set of fixed targets. While having a homogeneous distribution across the different categories is ideal, to ensure that the sample is truly representative of each local context, it may be more appropriate to prioritise representativeness over equality, aiming for a composition that reflects the real demographic and social characteristics of the local population. Therefore, the numbers and categories presented in the table are purely indicative.

Regarding the number of participants, although a minimum threshold will be guaranteed, the number of participants to be involved in each CSL will be determined within a range defined jointly with CSL coordinators, considering available resources, the scope of local activities, and the need for both locally relevant insights and meaningful cross-country comparability.

Stakeholders, on the other hand, are professional actors within each region's food system, identified by the CSL Coordinators. These include local authorities, research institutions, food producers, processors, retailers, the HoReCa sector, as well as third-sector and community-based organisations working to uphold the access to food. This participant group will be engaged at the end of the CSP to contribute to the groundwork for designing the BCIs. Subsequently, they will also be invited to participate in the implementation and evaluation of the BCIs, in the following phase of the project.

4.1.3 Alignment between the Digital Toolset and the methodological framework

The **Digital Toolset is a central instrument of the SPOON project**, consisting of a suite of interconnected digital solutions designed to empower citizens, researchers, and policymakers to transform food systems through data-driven innovation, CS, and secure digital interactions. The Toolset enables individuals to actively participate in research and decision-making while maintaining full sovereignty over their personal data. It plays a pivotal role in data collection, citizen engagement, and the co-design of behavioural solutions. To ensure consistency across all CSLs while allowing for contextual adaptation, the Toolset follows a shared narrative framework grounded in the food consumption journey, comprising the stages of planning, buying, storing, preparing, consuming, and disposal. This structure reflects the main phases of daily food-related behaviours and provides a coherent basis for organising both quantitative and qualitative insights.

Crucially, the food journey framework serves as the backbone for integrating the project's two core thematic areas:

- Understanding food habits to promote healthy and sustainable diets.
- Co-designing the functionalities of the Digital Toolset itself.

Each stage provides a natural entry point to explore both themes, as each iteration addresses at least one phase of the food cycle while also allowing participants to provide feedback on their experience with the Toolset's usability and purpose. Moreover, participation in SPOON is articulated through several key components of the Digital Toolset, which CSL participants engage with throughout implementation—both during workshops and, where feasible,

between sessions. This iterative, hybrid (online/offline) engagement model supports flexibility while enabling shared data structures and cumulative learning.

Among these key components, the following stand out:

- **User Interface:** Participants will test the accessibility and usability of the digital interface, including how the food journey is navigated. Feedback will be collected during in-person sessions and, optionally, through at-home use. In the early stages, CSLs may use paper prototypes or printed walkthroughs, especially in areas with limited digital access.
- **Visual Dashboard:** This dashboard-style tool will provide participants with feedback visualisations derived from collective data. CSLs will test the clarity, usefulness, and relevance of these visual outputs in fostering awareness and learning.
- **Data Wallet:** This feature enables participants to explore how their data is stored, accessed, and managed. CSLs will collect feedback on perceived transparency, control, and willingness to share personal data.
- **Data Privacy and Consent:** GDPR compliance will be embedded throughout the co-creation process. Participant concerns regarding data protection and associated risks will be openly discussed, and any resulting barriers will be documented and addressed collaboratively.
- **Digital Questionnaire:** A core module shared across all CSLs to collect structured data on food practices, perceptions, and values. It also allows for local adaptations to capture context-specific issues.

The Digital Toolset is not only a data collection system, but also a mechanism for empowering citizens to reflect on their behaviours and inform the design of BCIs. Feedback gathered on all Toolset components will be continuously channelled to JIBE, the partner responsible for the Toolset's development, to enable iterative improvements and ensure that SPOON's digital infrastructure remains both functionally robust and ethically sound.

To further support alignment across CSLs, a methodological guide and optional visual tools will be made available. These will clarify how digital components, food journey stages, and thematic subtopics interconnect, enabling CSL coordinators to implement activities consistently while maintaining the flexibility needed to address local priorities.

4.1.4 The Food Journal

The Food Journal is an **engagement tool** that has been incorporated into the SPOON methodology to maximise the productivity of the workshops on food practices, ensure continuity between iterations, foster long-term participant engagement, and strengthen the project's impact in terms of awareness-raising and self-reflection. The Food Journal consists of a **field diary** in the form of a **physical booklet** that enables workshop participants to document and monitor their own food practices across the five stages of the food consumption cycle from the consumer perspective. In doing so, the Food Journal mirrors the narrative structure of the iterations and of the Digital Toolset, ensuring a coherent and seamless articulation among the different methodological components of the project.

The diary is organised according to the **five stages of the food consumption cycle** and includes guided exercises that are concise, accessible, and dynamic. These exercises support participants in observing and reflecting on their food practices, helping them to become more aware of their actions, habits, and perceptions. These exercises may vary in duration. It is recommended that participants carry out the monitoring of their activities over the course of

one week, with the flexibility to choose the week that best fits their schedules. In addition, a follow-up process will be implemented to inform participants about the stage they are currently completing and to ensure that, on the day of the workshop, they attend the session having completed the relevant exercises. The content of the exercises is informed by the data requirements of the research and data analysis partners, ensuring the collection of relevant information for the development of the BCIs. At the same time, the exercises are designed to engage participants, promote awareness, and encourage a sense of ownership over the project.

This tool serves, on the one hand, as a bridge between iterations or workshops, allowing participants to remain connected to the project even during periods of lower activity. On the other hand, it enables a clearer operational distinction of the five food cycle stages within the CSP, specially because several stages are addressed jointly during a single iteration. Therefore, the Food Journal makes it possible to further segment the participation period within the CSP, enhancing participants' sense of progress and their experience of moving through a structured sequence of actions, while also helping to break monotony throughout the process. Moreover, the Food Journal helps to optimise the **knowledge exchange** during the workshops, as participants will have already engaged in preliminary reflection through common exercises. This preparation supports more focused discussions and facilitates the comparison of perspectives among attendees.

It is important to note that the use of the Food Journal is **not mandatory**. Rather, it is offered as a complementary activity within the project. Nevertheless, its use will be actively encouraged by CSL Coordinators, as it represents a highly valuable tool to foster participant commitment and ensure sustained engagement over time. The Food Journal will be jointly designed by SFC, CSCP, and ICONS. SFC will develop the structure and format of the exercises based on the data requirements defined by CSCP, while ICONS will be responsible for the final layout and production.

4.2 METHODOLOGY

The methodology described refers to the activities planned under the CSP, which are conceived as the central CS initiatives of the project. Within each CSL, citizens will act both as participants and co-researchers, engaging in successive iterations to collect, analyse, and interpret data collaboratively, thus directly contributing to the generation of scientific knowledge on sustainable and healthy food environments.

The CSL methodology is structured around two main goals:

1. Collecting insights to co-design the questionnaire through which the CSP will gather the data required to build the foundations for the BCIs.
2. Gathering feedback on the functionalities of the Digital Toolset to co-design its final version based on participants' input.

Both goals will be addressed through co-design workshops implemented by the CSLs Coordinators. However, each goal will rely on a different tool to maximise the impact of the workshops and the quality of the insights gathered during the collaborative sessions.

For the first goal, participants will complete an auto-ethnographic exercise using the Food Journal, which will serve as the basis for co-designing the questionnaire during the workshops. For the second goal, participants will be encouraged to use the Digital Toolset so they can test its functionalities and provide structured feedback. This combination allows for the

triangulation of qualitative and quantitative insights and aligns with the dual role of CSLs as both LLs and CS infrastructures.

The methodology is structured into 5 iterations that guide the implementation of the CSLs, forming a coherent, iterative process that aligns with both goals (**Figure 2**).

4.2.1 Iteration 1: The pre-pilot

This is an introductory phase of **one session** designed to lay the groundwork for the official launch of the pilot. It focuses on preparing all necessary components for the implementation of the CSP (**Table 4**).

Objectives: The pre-pilot aims to:

- Introducing SPOON and the concept of the CSL to participants.
- Validate prior research on food consumption behaviour and data privacy.
- Capture initial impressions and expectations on H&S systems to effectively inform the subsequent stages of the methodology.

Participants: Each session involves between 10 and 15 participants. Wherever possible, we recommend selecting participants from existing, already engaged communities within each CSL. These participants may also be involved in the broader pilot activities that follow.

Table 4. Workshop in Iteration 1.

	Description	Target
Session 1	Introduction to the project, presentation of the initiative to citizens, and discussion of initial topics related to the food system and data sharing.	10 to 15 consumers

4.2.2 Iteration 2: Planning and buying

This set of workshops is divided into two sessions: one focused on collecting data on capabilities, motivations, and opportunities to develop a questionnaire that allows for the analysis of consumers' food-related behaviours; and another aimed at co-designing the functionalities of the Digital Toolset (**Table 5**).

To provide a basis for co-designing the questions, each CSL will be given a set of preliminary questions to be validated or adapted with participants.

Objectives: This phase aims to:

- Explore behaviours around food planning and buying.
- Understand perceptions, motivations & drivers (COM-B, food environment framework).
- Identify cognitive & social influences (e.g. social norms, education, info exposure)
- Discuss the Digital Toolset (Data Wallet, Questionnaire, Data Lake, Dashboard)

Participants: A total of 12 to 20 participants per workshop should be involved. Although it is recommended that participants in the first workshop also attend the rest of them, it is acknowledged that maintaining the same group throughout may not always be feasible. Therefore, while some individuals may participate in all or several workshops, others may only join one of the sessions. In any case, it is advisable to ensure a similar number of participants in both workshops, ideally between 15 and 18 per session. This balance will help maintain continuity while allowing for some degree of flexibility in participation.

Table 5: Workshops in iteration 2.

	Description	Target
Food Journal exercises		
Workshop 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reflect on food planning and buying behaviour • Co-design the planning and buying-related questions from the Digital Toolset questionnaire 	12 to 20 consumers
Food Journal exercises		
Workshop 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-design one of the functionalities of the Digital Toolset. • Feedback on the concept and usability of the Digital Toolset Dashboard. • Feedback on the decentralized GDPR-compliant data sharing approach of DataU. 	12 to 20 consumers

4.2.3 Iteration 3: Storing, preparing and eating

This iteration follows the same structure as the previous one: one workshop dedicated to exploring consumers' food behaviours and another focused on co-designing the Digital Toolset, consisting of three sessions aimed at refining its various functionalities and allowing participants to propose modifications to its navigation and content (**Table 6**).

Objectives: The activities in this cluster aim to:

- Examine behaviours around food storage, preparation & consumption
- Focus on sustainability, health & resource efficiency
- Continue iterative feedback on the Digital Toolset

Participants: As in the previous iteration, each workshop should involve between 12 and 20 participants. Ideally, those attending the first workshop in this iteration would also participate in the remaining sessions. However, it is recognised that keeping the same group throughout may not always be possible. Consequently, while some individuals may take part in all or several workshops, others may join only one session. In any case, it is recommended to maintain a similar number of participants in each workshop—ideally between 15 and 18—to

ensure continuity while allowing for flexibility. Participants from Iterations 1 and 2 should also join iteration 3, although this is not mandatory.

Table 6: Workshops in iteration 3.

	Description	Target
Workshop 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reflect on food storing, preparing and eating behaviour. • Co-design the storing, preparing and eating-related questions from the Digital Toolset questionnaire 	12 to 20 consumers
Food Journal exercises		
Workshop 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feedback on the concept and usability of the Digital Toolset Dashboard Personal Data Wallet. • Feedback on the navigation of the Digital Toolset questionnaire • Co-design session to propose adjustments 	12 to 20 consumers

4.2.4 Iteration 4: Leftovers and waste management

This iteration follows the same structure as the previous ones. In this case, the workshop focused on content will address the disposal phase of the food cycle. As for the second workshop, instead of concentrating on a single functionality of the Digital Toolset, it will collect comprehensive feedback and insights to refine the tool from an integrated perspective (**Table 7**).

Objectives: The activities in this iteration aim to:

- Explore behaviours on managing leftovers, food storage & disposal
- Address circular behaviours & attitudes to food waste
- Collect participant input for refining the Digital Toolset

Participants: As in the previous iteration, each workshop should involve between 12 and 20 participants. Ideally, those attending the first workshop in this iteration would also participate in the remaining sessions. However, it is recognised that keeping the same group throughout may not always be possible. Consequently, while some individuals may take part in all or several workshops, others may join only one session. In any case, it is recommended to maintain a similar number of participants in each workshop—ideally between 15 and 18—to ensure continuity while allowing for flexibility. Participants from Iterations 1 and 2 should also join iteration 3, although this is not mandatory.

Table 7: Workshops in Iteration 4.

	Description	Target
Workshop 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reflect on food waste and disposal behaviour. • Co-design the disposing and waste management related questions from the Digital Toolset questionnaire 	12 to 20 consumers
Round of Digital Toolset - Questionnaire testing		
Workshop 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feedback on the concept and usability of the Personal Data Wallet. • Feedback on the navigation of the Digital Toolset questionnaire • Co-design session to propose adjustments 	12 to 20 consumers

4.2.5 Iteration 5: Knowledge building

This iteration is designed both to provide participants with a return of results and to serve as a platform for promoting the Digital Toolset within the region, with the aim of attracting new, non-moderated citizen scientists. In addition, the cluster includes a workshop dedicated to interpreting the results obtained throughout the CSP, in order to generate the knowledge that will form the foundation for the design of the BCIs (**Table 8**).

Objectives: This phase is intended to:

- Return of knowledge and results of all the gathered data to the participants.
- Interpret participant-generated data on the consumer's food journey.
- Co-design the research questions to assess the BCIs in each CSL.
- Set the foundations for the design of the BCIs.
- Spread the use of the Digital toolset and its questionnaire.

Participants: This final phase seeks to bring together both stakeholders and consumers who have and have not participated in previous workshops. Although it consists of a single workshop and recognising that some participants may not remain engaged until the end of the process, we anticipate attendance of approximately 15 to 25 individuals.

Table 8: Workshop in iteration 5.

	Description	Target
Workshop 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interpretation of all the results produced with all the data collected along the CSP to set the foundations for the design of the BCIs • Co-design of the research question for each CSL to assess the BCIs. 	15 to 25 participants, including both stakeholders and consumers.

Figure 2: Iteration outline.

5 STAKEHOLDER MAPPING, RECRUITMENT AND ENGAGEMENT STRATEGIES

5.1 STAKEHOLDER MAPPING

As part of WP3, under Task 3.2: *Mapping of actors and value chains in food and related sectors in CSL regions*, each CSL was asked to identify the food system actors they aimed to involve in their pilots. Once these stakeholders were mapped, a workshop was held on the 26th June 2025 to explore the specific needs, barriers, and motivations that might influence the engagement of each stakeholder type in the SPOON project. Although each CSL mapped a diverse range of actors, some groups were consistently identified across all regions. These were local authorities and policymakers, research organisations and academia, and community initiatives and third-sector entities. Other categories of stakeholders with significant presence included food producers, processors and manufacturers, retailers, and the HoReCa sector. It is worth noting that stakeholders specifically related to health and nutrition were only suggested by one CSL.

Figure 3: Stakeholder mapping workshop with the CSLs

Given this stakeholder typology, and the need for a harmonised and centralised methodology, it is crucial to ensure that the types of stakeholders participating in the co-creation workshops are as consistent as possible across the six CSLs. This is particularly important in Phase 5, where stakeholders will assess the proposals developed by citizens and co-develop the foundation for the BCIs, to be designed in the subsequent stage of the project, Task 4.2: *Behaviour Change Interventions*.

The following section presents a detailed analysis of the needs and motivations identified during the stakeholder engagement workshop, as well as the barriers, to effectively involve each actor type.

5.1.1 Local authorities

As identified in the workshop, the motivations for participating in SPOON for local authorities are related to these three topics:

- **Strategic Political Positioning through participatory processes.** Participation in the SPOON project offers local authorities and public administrations a valuable opportunity to strengthen their political positioning by aligning with democratic and citizen-centred governance models. Through SPOON, these institutions can visibly reinforce their commitment to transparency, proximity to citizens, and the democratization of knowledge. Moreover, the project serves as a testbed for experimenting with collaborative methods and participatory approaches that bring public institutions closer to society.
- **Food policy development and knowledge-driven design.** SPOON provides local authorities with the opportunity to design and implement local food strategies that combine health and sustainability objectives, informed by citizens' experiences. In addition, the project enables public administrations to deepen their understanding of the local food ecosystem. The conceptualisation and development of local food strategies are supported by access to data, both formal and informal, which can enrich existing knowledge and inform the evolution of current strategies. Some of these actions may also relate to innovative initiatives aimed at enhancing food security or establishing/promoting local food councils.
- **Territorial knowledge and resource optimization.** Participating in the SPOON project alongside other organisations allows local authorities to become more familiar with key stakeholders in their territory and to map potential collaborations with local actors. This territorial engagement enhances their capacity to optimise available resources, strengthens existing initiatives and fosters opportunities for future partnerships related to local food strategies. Additionally, it offers a valuable interface for public administrations to collaborate directly with academia, thereby strengthening the connection between policy, research, and societal needs.

Several barriers have been identified that may hinder the involvement of local authorities and public administrations in the SPOON project. These can be grouped into the following areas:

- **Lack of a participatory governance framework.** The absence of established governance models that actively include citizens in decision-making processes makes local authorities not accustomed to engaging the public beyond consultation or communication, which can generate hesitation or resistance. Participating in a project like SPOON may be perceived as risky if administrations fear raising expectations they are not institutionally or politically prepared to meet.
- **Limited human and financial resources.** Many local authorities face resource constraints, both in terms of budget and personnel, that hinder their participation in additional initiatives. The lack of staff or funding to support participation in CS projects often results in limited engagement or the inability to follow through with implementation and follow-up actions.

- **Competing priorities within local agendas.** Local authorities are often required to address a wide range of urgent and cross-cutting issues. In this context, food-related topics may not be perceived as a priority, despite their strategic relevance. The high number of competing demands on municipal agendas can lead to limited attention and institutional bandwidth for engaging in external projects.

5.1.2 Research centres and academia

Participation in SPOON offers researchers and academic institutions several relevant opportunities that go beyond data collection and knowledge transfer. These motivations can be summarised as follows:

- **Access to real-world environment local data.** SPOON provides researchers with access to context-specific data generated in real-world settings through a bottom-up approach. These practical case studies offer valuable insights into food behaviours and socio-demographic dynamics, helping to identify new research questions and enhancing the social relevance of academic work.
- **Strengthen collaboration with local communities.** The project fosters direct collaboration between researchers, citizens, and local food system actors. These interactions support the development of more inclusive and socially embedded research practices while opening new avenues for networking and future cooperation at the local level.
- **Pathways to market.** By bridging academic research with societal needs, SPOON can help researchers identify the practical implications and potential applications of their work. This includes opportunities to contribute to local innovation ecosystems and explore market-oriented developments related to sustainable and healthy food systems.

Among the barriers, these can be distributed in two topics:

- **Lack of monetary incentives.** Researchers may be reluctant to participate without financial compensation. Ensuring their long-term commitment can be challenging in the absence of monetary incentives.
- **Methodological and institutional barriers.** Some researchers may lack familiarity with participatory approaches or CS methodologies, leading them to question the validity or relevance of the research outputs. Additionally, differing priorities between researchers and the project objectives may result in a lack of engagement or interest.
- **Access to data.** Researchers involved in the project might not have full access to data collected from the various sources within the initiative, which can limit their involvement or trust in the process.
- **Institutional competition:** Competition between research institutions may also act as a barrier, particularly in contexts where data sharing, or recognition are contested.

5.1.3 Food producers, processors and manufacturers

The main motivations for these actors to engage in the SPOON project can be grouped into the following three areas:

- **Market visibility and brand positioning.** Participation in SPOON offers the possibility to increase market visibility and promote a brand image aligned with transparency, sustainability, and responsible production practices. Moreover, involvement in such a project can help convey an approachable, engaged, and environmentally responsible corporate profile. This can be particularly attractive to conscious consumers who value ethical and environmentally friendly food systems.
- **Understanding consumer perceptions and needs.** By participating in the project, producers and manufacturers can gain valuable insights into consumers' perceptions of health and sustainability in food products. This includes understanding which indicators or attributes are most relevant to consumers when making purchasing decisions, as well as identifying emerging needs and expectations in the market.
- **Adopting sustainable practices and enhancing product offering.** SPOON can serve as a platform for learning about sustainable practices, including effective resource use, waste reduction strategies, and communication tools to better differentiate products in the marketplace. It can also offer guidance on how to make sustainable food more accessible and convenient for consumers.
- **Networking and collaboration.** The project facilitates interaction and collaboration with other stakeholders across the food system, enabling the sharing of knowledge, experiences, and resources. This can support future partnerships and foster innovation within the sector.

While several motivations support the involvement of food sector actors in SPOON, the following barriers have been identified as potential obstacles to their active participation:

- **Reluctance to share data.** Although the exchange of information and resources is one of the potential benefits of participating in SPOON, some producers and manufacturers may be hesitant to share data related to their practices or products. This reluctance may stem from concerns about transparency, fear of negative comparisons with competitors, or uncertainty about how shared data might impact their brand or commercial operations. Additionally, maintaining regular data-sharing practices may be seen as burdensome or incompatible with the pace of daily business activities.
- **Limited time and human resources.** Participation in a CS project requires time and a degree of organisational commitment. For many actors in the food sector, the time required to engage in meetings, activities, or data collection may represent a significant constraint and reduce their capacity to contribute consistently.
- **Lack of participatory culture.** Some stakeholders may be unfamiliar with or sceptical about the value of collaborative approaches such as CS. This scepticism may translate into limited interest or trust in the effectiveness of participatory activities, especially when their concrete benefits are not immediately visible or aligned with business priorities.

5.1.4 Retailers

As the food producers, processors and manufacturers; the motivations of retailers also include:

- **Market visibility and brand positioning.** Participation in SPOON offers retailers the opportunity to promote the social value of their businesses and foster a brand image based on transparency, sustainability, and responsible supply chain practices. This positioning can translate into increased consumer trust, higher sales, and enhanced reputation.
- **Understanding consumer perceptions and needs.** Through the project, retailers can gain valuable insights into consumers' behaviours and preferences regarding healthy and sustainable food. This information can help them adapt their product offerings and implement targeted actions to stimulate demand and better meet customer expectations.
- **Networking and collaboration.** SPOON facilitates connections with local authorities and other stakeholders across the food system, creating opportunities for future partnerships, shared initiatives, and collaborative projects.
- **Involvement in experimental actions.** Retailers can actively contribute to the implementation of pilot interventions and assess their real-world impact. This allows them to test innovative practices and determine their effectiveness in a practical setting.

While some of the barriers identified for consumers may also apply to retailers, the following challenges were specifically highlighted during the workshop:

- **Fear of negative comparison.** Retailers may be concerned about being publicly compared to other businesses and facing criticism. This perception of exposure can discourage participation.
- **Lack of experience with participatory processes.** Many retailers may have limited or no experience with participatory or community-based initiatives. This lack of participatory culture can make engagement more difficult, and coordinating with such actors can pose practical challenges due to internal hierarchies or rigid operational structures, especially with large corporate chains.
- **Uncertainty about outcomes and impact.** Retailers may hesitate to participate due to doubts about the effect of their contribution. Specifically, there may be uncertainty about whether their involvement will translate into positive consumer responses or measurable improvements in sales.
- **Misalignment with project objectives.** Misalignment can arise for various reasons. On the one hand, healthy and sustainable food options may be perceived as expensive, potentially discouraging participation. On the other hand, some retailers may wish to use consumer data for private commercial purposes, which could conflict with the ethical framework or collective goals of the project.

5.1.5 HoReCa sector

The motivations detected are the following:

- **Market visibility and brand positioning.** Participation in SPOON offers the HoReCa sector the opportunity to promote the social value of their businesses and foster a brand image based on transparency, sustainability, and responsible practices. This positioning can translate into increased consumer trust, higher sales, and enhanced reputation.
- **Understanding consumer perceptions and needs.** Through the project, they can gain valuable insights into consumers' behaviours and preferences regarding healthy and sustainable food. Also, in the case of Bruges, their contribution to the project can help the sector to reach more local consumers.
- **Networking and collaboration.** SPOON facilitates connections with other stakeholders across the food system.
- **Adopting sustainable practices on food waste.** The HoReCa companies can learn new practices, especially in the food waste topic that can be profitable for them when reducing cost and adding some value to their brand.

The barriers identified can be around these topics:

- **Presence of high hierarchy.** The company may be strongly guided by hierarchical structures and top-down strategic objectives, which can hinder alignment with the priorities established by the SPOON project.
- **Economic constraints.** Lack of economic interest may stem from the absence of immediate or short-term benefits, as well as from the perception that healthy and sustainable food is costly, making it a domain they are reluctant to engage with.
- **Fear of criticism.** Companies may be hesitant to participate due to concerns if their practices are compared to those of other businesses.

5.1.6 Third sector and community initiatives

Due to their strong culture of citizen participation and social engagement, these actors are generally well-positioned and likely to be receptive to participating. Although third sector organisations and community initiatives were discussed as separate groups, the perspectives expressed regarding their involvement in the SPOON project were largely aligned.

- **Collaboration and deep engagement with citizens.** The project offers valuable opportunities for networking with other stakeholders and fostering direct relationships with citizens. This facilitates stronger future collaboration and mutual learning among different community-led initiatives working towards similar objectives.
- **Shared goals and common priorities.** Participation in the project can help reinforce shared goals, such as strengthening local communities, promoting food security, and advancing social inclusion.
- **Knowledge sharing.** The project creates a space for the participants to share their expertise, contribute proposals, and voice the needs of the communities they represent. It also allows for the collection of data that can inform policies and help address the needs

of vulnerable groups. In turn, this participatory process can contribute to citizen empowerment and promote greater civic engagement in food-related decision-making.

Although these actors demonstrate a strong participatory profile and high potential for engagement in the SPOON project, several barriers must be taken into consideration:

- **Limited time and human resources.** These organisations often lack time and human resources, which can hinder both recruitment and long-term engagement. Also, despite some of these organisations rely on volunteers, managing volunteers is significantly demanding.
- **Data and ethical concerns.** Some organisations may be protective of their communities and reluctant to share data without full clarity on its use, especially if they fear misuse or greenwashing. Trust and transparency are essential to address these concerns.
- **Technological limitations.** Not all organisations have the infrastructure to support digital participation. However, this is expected to be managed by the CSLs reducing the burden on participants.

5.2 RECRUITMENT STRATEGIES

5.2.1 Participant roles for the recruitment

Building upon Task 3.2, a set of recruitment strategies has been designed to ensure the successful implementation of participatory methodologies within the SPOON project. These strategies are informed by two key dimensions: the profile of the participants and the purpose of their involvement.

As already detailed in 4.1.2 *Target audiences and purpose*, participants fall broadly into two categories —consumers and stakeholders— each with distinct characteristics and roles within the project. On the one hand, the project aims to engage a diverse spectrum of citizens, representative of each CSL region. Due to the wide diversity of profiles reflecting the intersectionality of demographic characteristics, the recruitment strategy focuses on engaging multipliers to reach broad population segments divided according to age and level of common representation; resulting in the general public, older adults, youth, and vulnerable groups.

On the other hand, stakeholders are grouped as described in the previous section. In addition to these, **knowledge brokers** play a crucial role, acting as intermediaries who help translate academic and scientific concepts into accessible language for the general public.

The second dimension shaping the recruitment strategy is the **purpose of participation**. Participants may engage in various ways:

- Those involved in the **pre-pilot phase**, including both consumers and stakeholders, who will contribute to shaping the methodology and the development of the digital tool.
- Those participating in the **subsequent workshops**, where citizens and stakeholders collaboratively analyse challenges, interpret data, and co-create solutions.
- Individuals who will interact with the **Digital Toolset**, either to provide data on their food habits or to report on their user experience and contribute feedback.
- **Knowledge brokers**, who will facilitate understanding and uptake by making the project more accessible.

- **Stakeholders**, who will play a central role in designing and implementing BCIs in a later stage of the project, specifically under Task 4.2.

5.2.2 Recruitment Strategies

During the workshop held on 26th June, a set of risk mitigation measures was identified, addressing both recruitment and engagement challenges for both consumer and stakeholder profiles. Recruitment strategies for citizens and the identification of knowledge brokers was also appointed (**Figure 4**).

Figure 4: Recruitment strategies for citizens and knowledge brokers identified by the CSLs

At a global level, the following strategic communication actions were defined as essential to support recruitment:

- Clearly communicate the **identity** of the project team – "Who we are".
- Clearly define **SPOON's goals and vision**.
- Specify the **target groups** and their potential roles.
- Transparently present the **engagement process** and expectations for participants.

All project communication materials must be **clear and accessible**. The use of simple language, visual elements (e.g. icons), and short, engaging messages is encouraged. QR codes can be used to give interested individuals direct access to additional information. Suggested motivational messages include: *"Take back control over your food choices," "Shape your local food map," "Hold retailers accountable,"* or *"Stop being nudged into junk."*

To maximise outreach, recruitment will also rely on **digital channels and strategic partnerships**. Social media platforms will be used to reach diverse profiles, and collaboration with **food bloggers, influencers, or local community initiatives** will further expand visibility. Regarding consumer recruitment, several complementary actions can enhance the effectiveness of the campaign. **Awareness-raising activities** will support online outreach and

should include **at least two in-person info sessions per CSL**, as well as **engagement initiatives** such as guided walks or food-related tours. Furthermore, since participation is voluntary and cannot be financially compensated, the campaign must emphasize both the **intrinsic value of engagement** and the possibility of receiving **symbolic incentives**.

To strengthen **trust and transparency**, recruitment communications must clearly explain how participant data will be used, analysed, stored, and who will retain ownership. **Likewise**, the inclusion of **students** was identified as a strategic opportunity, given their potential involvement either as citizens, interns, or through academic projects aligned with SPOON's objectives. Their participation could also serve as an indirect entry point to engage **educators** and academic institutions.

To expand dissemination, retailers will also be considered active contributors to the campaign. They will be provided with ready-to-use communication and educational materials to facilitate outreach, while simultaneously reinforcing their sustainable brand identity and engaging their customer base.

When approaching private sector stakeholders (e.g. producers, retailers, HoReCa), the recruitment strategy should align with their corporate values, especially where these intersect with SPOON's commitment to health and sustainability. To minimise barriers, participation should be framed around light and flexible formats, such as involvement in specific activities or events, rather than long-term commitments. Moreover, direct outreach to company representatives and managers is recommended to ensure more personalised invitations and to clearly present the project's goals and the specific roles they can play.

Finally, the implementation of recognition mechanisms, such as symbolic awards or digital green badges for individuals or organisations, is encouraged. These forms of acknowledgment can help build a shared sense of ownership, foster a collective identity, and further motivate continued engagement.

Bearing in mind all these characteristics and risk mitigations, the recruitment strategy will be executed in several actions, tailored to the roles and profiles involved:

1. Pre-pilot participants (consumers and stakeholders) will be recruited through the existing networks of CSL coordinators via direct contact.
2. To engage consumers for the pilot workshops, each CSL will rely on local multipliers to disseminate information and stimulate interest. A *snowball* approach will be used, encouraging participants to share the invitation within their communities. Social media channels of the CSL coordinators will amplify this outreach, alongside the launch of each CSLs Local Desk and a registration form. To increase the campaign's effectiveness, customised messaging will be designed for each consumer segment (e.g. elderly, youth, vulnerable groups).
3. To reach consumers using the Digital Toolset, the tool will be presented during workshops, where participants will be invited to promote it within their circles. The campaign will also be supported on social media with posts encouraging the public to explore and use the tool.
4. Stakeholders will be approached through a dual strategy: targeted outreach from the CSL coordinators' networks, complemented by broader digital dissemination within food-related ecosystems. A *snowball* effect is also expected here, as directly engaged stakeholders may help recruit others.

5.2.3 Timeline

The most intensive phase of the recruitment campaign will be launched during the last quarter of 2025. Since the project aims to involve participants from the very start and retain their engagement throughout the various workshops up to the final results-sharing phase, concentrating efforts during this timeframe is both strategic and necessary. The recruitment actions implemented during this phase are expected to secure the majority of volunteers who will contribute consistently across the different stages of the project. However, as Phase 0 is parallel to the implementation of the recruitment campaign, participants involved in the Pre-Pilot will primarily be recruited through direct outreach via the existing networks of the CSL Coordinators, rather than through the broader public campaign.

Following the main recruitment campaign, continuous monitoring of participant engagement will be carried out to track the level of sustained involvement. Based on this monitoring, targeted micro-campaigns may be activated, where needed, to replace participants who drop out and ensure sufficient attendance at all subsequent workshops. These participant tracking actions will include targeted communications via registration forms and, if necessary, personalised email follow-up with participants.

5.3 THE ENGAGEMENT STRATEGIES

Given the **need to ensure continuous and active participation across the project's timeline**—both in terms of workshop attendance and consistent use of the Digital Toolset—it is **essential to deploy a range of long-term engagement strategies that go beyond initial recruitment efforts**. These strategies are structured around three core dimensions: content, structure, and interaction.

From a content perspective, although it is also linked to structural dimension, the narrative logic underpinning the participatory methodology—centred on the consumer's food cycle—not only provides a coherent framework for data collection, but also operates as a strategic engagement mechanism. By dividing the process into distinct, time-bound phases that allow participants to explore food-related practices in a sequential manner, the project creates a framework where citizen scientists can clearly perceive their advancement and the cumulative impact of their contributions. Each phase builds upon the previous one, providing participants with a tangible feeling of continuity and purpose. This perception of progress is critical for sustaining motivation and avoiding disengagement or fatigue over time.

To reinforce this progress and the productivity of the co-creation sessions and the essential role of participants, each phase culminates in a tangible output or visual product that is shared with the participants. From an engagement point of view, sharing these intermediate outcomes between phases not only serve to mark transitions between phases but also reinforce participants' role as co-creators of knowledge, remind them of upcoming activities, encourage ongoing use of the Digital Toolset, and express the project team's appreciation. It provides a natural opportunity for CSL Coordinators to maintain contact with participants and facilitate ongoing engagement through lighter monitoring activities.

Equally important is the design of inter-phase activities, such as the Food Journal. This tool acts as a bridge between workshops, fostering continuity and helping participants transition smoothly from one phase to the next. Moreover, the reflective nature of these activities increases participant involvement, strengthens their connection to the project, and enhances

their willingness to exchange ideas, share personal observations, and engage in collective reflection.

On a structural level, **SPOON's engagement strategy is both iterative and adaptive.** Committing to a year-long participatory project, with outcomes that will only materialise in the long term, poses a challenge. Therefore, different levels of engagement have been carefully defined. The division of the methodology into autonomous phases allows individuals to decide the extent of their involvement; whether they wish to take part in a single phase, multiple ones, or the entire process. Furthermore, providing participants with the option to choose their level of involvement—particularly important for stakeholders with limited time or resources—reinforces flexibility as a key driver of sustained engagement and accommodates individual availability but also facilitates the recruitment of new participants throughout the pilot.

The possibility to choose the level of involvement applies not only to the number of workshops attended but also to the types of activities undertaken. For instance, while participation in the Food Journal is encouraged, it remains optional. Those with greater interest or availability can engage more deeply, while others may limit their participation to workshop attendance alone.

Moreover, these varying levels of commitment are also differentiated by participant profile. While consumers are expected to be more consistently engaged throughout Task 4.1 (from October 2025 to January 2027), stakeholder involvement is more focused, primarily during the two pre-pilot phases and again at the end of the process, when they are invited to assess the citizen-generated proposals.

Participants will have the possibility to engage with the process through both physical and digital means, with their experiences directly feeding into the design of tools. As such, The Digital Toolset will be presented as a central and indispensable component of the CSL activities. Nevertheless, recognising the digital divide, the project also ensures accessibility for individuals who may not have the necessary skills or resources. Likewise, participation in the workshops is not a prerequisite for using the Toolset; individuals may engage with the platform asynchronously and provide feedback through alternative channels provided by the Digital Toolset.

In parallel, SPOON will seek to connect with ongoing food-related initiatives in each region. This alignment with local contexts increases the project's relevance and resonance for participants—particularly stakeholders—and reinforces their motivation to remain involved.

From an interaction standpoint, maintaining regular, meaningful contact with participants is crucial. This ensures they remain well-informed about project developments and their role within it, thereby fostering trust and a sense of inclusion. Offering clear points of contact and prompt responses to questions reinforces a feeling of support and guidance throughout the participant's journey. The fact that participants never feel alone and can count on the SPOON team's support at any moment plays a key role in sustaining their engagement and reinforcing their commitment to the project.

All project communications—whether in meetings, written materials, or digital content—will clearly articulate objectives, expected outcomes, and next steps. Demonstrating tangible progress and involving participants in each stage of decision-making helps ensure they perceive their contributions as valuable and impactful.

Taken together, these strategies—combined with the leadership of the CSL Coordinators, a focus on issues that are directly relevant to participants, a shared governance approach, and

purpose-driven activities— closely resemble the development of a community of practice. Drawing on this methodological inspiration, SPOON workshops will be designed not only as moments of participation but also as dynamic spaces for ongoing communication, feedback, and collective learning. These sessions will incorporate capacity-building and peer-learning components to foster a collaborative, inclusive, and empowering environment. In this sense, to keep participants engaged the long run they should be treated as reliable partners from the early stages.

6 COMPETENCES, ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES

6.1 IMPLEMENTATION OF THE CSLs

The implementation of the CSLs is carried out by the CSLs Coordinators, who are responsible for developing and conducting the different activities with citizens, in collaboration with the other WP leaders. Their objective is to collect data from participants for use within the project and to provide continuous support and guidance throughout their engagement.

1. Implementation of the CSL activities

This activity encompasses all tasks related to the implementation of the sessions (both in-person and online) conducted by the CSLs with participants in each region.

This activity is structured around the following key tasks:

- **Event management and logistics:** This involves all logistical preparations, including determining the venue (for in-person sessions) or platform (for online sessions), setting the date and time, and establishing the overall schedule.
- **Participant convening:** This task focuses on contacting the participants who have already been recruited. It includes disseminating essential information regarding the location, date, and timing of the activity. Furthermore, participants will be briefed on the session's objectives and any preparatory requirements.
- **Workshop design:** The CSL Coordinators are responsible for designing the session agenda and the associated activities that structure the workshop. This design process will be executed in accordance with the guidelines and instructions provided by the data analysis team (CSCP).
- **Session facilitation and data collection:** The sessions will be conducted by the CSL Coordinators, who will lead the session and guide participants through the planned activities. Concurrently, during the facilitation, the CSL Coordinators are responsible for collecting relevant data pertaining to both the session's operational execution (e.g., timing, engagement) and the substantive content addressed.

2. Recruitment activities

This activity consists of a series of tasks aimed at recruiting individuals interested in participating in the various activities of the SPOON project within each CSL. The recruitment strategies that each CSL can utilize are multiple and discretionary, but some universal concepts apply.

- **Upload content in social media:** Following the instructions from ICONS, the CSLs are responsible for uploading the pertinent information to their respective social networks in the local language, as well as to translate the information to local language.

- **Contact potential participants through mail or phone:** In many cases, it will be necessary to contact potential participants via direct channels, such as telephone or email, to secure their participation in the project.
- **Follow-up of the people interested to participate:** To ensure that interested individuals ultimately participate, it is necessary to conduct a follow-up with the persons in question, either by confirming their attendance or by recording the reasons for their non-attendance.

3. Engagement activities

Although the engagement activities can also be discretionary, there is one task that must be compulsory for all CSLs.

- **Follow-up of the participants:** The CSLs must act as the liaison between the participants and the rest of the project. Therefore, and to guarantee participant engagement, the CSL Coordinators must act as guides for the participants, providing support whenever necessary and responding to their questions and doubts. This follow-up can be conducted in various ways and through different channels. Each CSL is free to choose its preferred method.

4. Data transfer

This activity is closely linked to the collaboration between the CSL Coordinators and the project partner responsible for coordination and data analysis. While the CSL Coordinators are in charge of collecting data, the data analysis partner is responsible for processing and analysing it. Therefore, a rigorous and efficient data transfer process must be ensured. To achieve this, several tasks must be performed:

- **Data collection:** During the workshops, each CSL must gather different types of information according to the data analysis partner's specifications. The same partner will provide detailed guidance on what data needs to be collected and how.
- **Data processing:** After each workshop, the CSLs must complete a reporting template provided by CSCP, summarising the main findings and insights from the session.
- **Translation to English:** All collected information must be translated into English prior to being transferred to CSCP to ensure consistency and comparability across all CSLs.

5. Impact assessment

In order to provide the partner responsible for the impact assessment of the project with the necessary information to conduct an accurate impact assessment in line with the established Impact Assessment Framework, the CSLs will also be required to carry out several tasks:

- **Impact assessment meetings:** At regular intervals, the CSLs will meet online with AIT to discuss the implementation of the methodology, participants' reception of the project, and the overall progress of SPOON. These meetings will serve to identify strengths, challenges, and opportunities for improvement in real time.
- **Information Gathering:** CSLs will collect qualitative and quantitative data on participants' engagement, behavioural changes, and local outcomes to support AIT in measuring the

project's impact. The data gathered will be reported using the templates and procedures defined by AIT to ensure consistency across all regions.

6. Communication and dissemination

All communication and dissemination activities are coordinated under WP7, led by ICONS. However, certain tasks must be implemented directly by the CSLs to ensure effective local outreach and visibility.

- **Communication tasks:** CSLs are responsible for translating the communication materials provided by ICONS into their local languages to guarantee accessibility and cultural relevance.
- **Content transfer:** CSLs must provide ICONS with communication materials — including photos, videos, and texts — that support the project's overall communication and dissemination objectives.

6.2 GUIDANCE, MENTORSHIP AND TRAINING

This set of activities corresponds to the intervention of the methodological team (SFC), together with ILVO, which are responsible for guiding the project from a methodological perspective and providing support to the CSLs to facilitate the development of their activities.

- **Coordination of the methodology:** ensure that all partners work together efficiently in order to achieve the goals of the project and maintain a comfortable workflow for all partners.
- **Guidance for the CSL:** SFC is responsible for providing support, feedback, and advice to the CSLs on any matter related to methodology, as well as on all activities they must carry out, except those related to data transfer and communication and dissemination. Therefore, SFC must:
 - Answer any question regarding methodology
 - Support CSLs in recruitment activities
 - Support CSLs in the design of workshops
 - Support CSLs in participant follow-up activities.

Moreover, SFC will create and share tools to mentor the CSLs in the above-mentioned activities, in order to train, support, and share knowledge asynchronously, enabling a peer-learning process throughout the project.

- **Training and capacity-building:** as part of the guidance activities, training and Q&A sessions will be organised to address common issues faced by the CSLs so that they can better handle the tasks related to their role. In addition, meetings and workshops will be organised between WP leaders and CSLs whenever necessary to ensure the transfer of knowledge required for CSL Coordinators to correctly perform their functions and contribute to improving the project outputs.
- **Monitoring of the methodology:** SFC will also support the implementation of the CSLs in order to monitor methodological activities and ensure that everything works properly. This will make it possible to modify the methodology if something does not work as expected and can be improved through methodological adjustments.

6.3 IMPLEMENTATION AND DATA ANALYSIS

The partner responsible for coordinating the implementation and analysing the data gathered by all CSLs, with the contribution of the research partners, is CSCP. Their activities include the following tasks:

- **Planning of the implementation:** CSCP is responsible for preparing a provisional schedule for each workshop, taking into account the needs of the CSLs and other partners to ensure smooth implementation. When designing this plan, citizen participation must also be considered; therefore, factors such as summer breaks and public holidays should be taken into account. This planning is essential to guarantee proper coordination among all partners. Although the plan can remain flexible, it must be sufficiently structured to allow all partners to work at a common pace and direction, ensuring efficient organisation.
- **Content transfer:** Just as SFC oversees how the CSLs implement their activities, CSCP is responsible for the content. It is therefore their role to generate all the necessary materials to inform the CSLs about what workshops must be carried out and what data need to be collected. This transfer of materials will be done through templates and guidance documents developed by CSCP. Depending on whether the document transmits or collects information, it will be filled in either by CSCP or by the CSLs.
 - **Documents issued by CSCP:**
 - **Workshop information sheet:** detailing the topics to be addressed during the workshop, the overall objective and its relevance within the project context, the rationale for addressing each topic, and the intended outcomes. It should also include a description of the specific subjects to be discussed, guiding questions, illustrative examples to contextualise them, and the type of responses expected.
 - **Preliminary questionnaires:** for workshops addressing the consumer food cycle, CSCP will provide a preliminary questionnaire covering each stage of the cycle. This document will later be co-created with citizens to ensure local and cultural contextualisation.
 - **Documents provided by CSCP but completed by CSL Coordinators:**
 - Attendance list
 - Demographic data template
 - Session evaluation form
 - Data collection template for each workshop
- **Data analysis:** CSCP is responsible for analysing the data provided by the CSLs using two complementary approaches, each serving different objectives:
 - **Analysis of data collected through workshop templates.** These data pursue two main objectives, depending on their focus:
 - **Data on participants' eating habits:** CSCP will analyse these data to develop a universal questionnaire structured around the five stages of the consumer food cycle, enabling comparison across regions.

- **Data on the functioning and navigation of the Digital Toolset:** CSCP will use these insights to identify strengths and weaknesses in the Digital Toolset and share relevant feedback with the responsible partners.
- **Analysis of data collected through the Digital Toolset:** these data primarily concern consumer food behaviour and, together with the information gathered during the workshops, will form the basis for the co-creation of the BCIs.

6.4 KNOWLEDGE BROKERS

The Knowledge Brokers act as intermediaries between the project's researchers and the participants. They are involved throughout the entire CSLs process, serving as facilitators of learning, translators of insights, and connectors who align citizen-generated knowledge with the project's broader, system-level objectives. Specifically, their responsibilities include:

- Bridging scientific knowledge and citizens' understanding.
- Interpreting local data within the broader SPOON framework.
- Ensuring consistency, quality, and comparability across countries.
- Strengthening feedback loops between participants and decision-makers.
- Supporting the dissemination of the project itself and the project's outcomes.

In light of these activities, a co-creation workshop was organised with the CSLs to identify the characteristics and skills required for the Knowledge Broker profile to perform their role effectively. Among the most valued attributes were expertise in food science, familiarity with the project and its objectives, and a strong understanding of the local context. The workshop also reached consensus on the importance of creativity, communication skills, and the ability to interact effectively with citizens. Furthermore, this person should be able to inspire trust, show genuine motivation for the project, demonstrate availability to undertake the required tasks, and be willing to do so on a voluntary basis.

Given the difficulty of finding a single individual who possesses all these qualities and is also able to dedicate personal time to the project, two options were considered. First, that the Knowledge Broker role does not necessarily have to be fulfilled by one person; instead, the related tasks can be distributed among several individuals depending on their skills. Second, that the CSLs Coordinators represent the most suitable profiles to assume these responsibilities. Positioned between the citizens and the research partners, they are familiar with the local context, maintain direct contact with participants, and possess strong communication and creative abilities that can greatly contribute to the success of the activities. Furthermore, given that they play an active part in the project, they have a good understanding of its aim and development.

Therefore, these responsibilities will be undertaken by the CSLs Coordinators, as they largely align with their existing duties. However, if any CSL lacks a specific expertise required to cover all Knowledge Broker functions, they may appoint an external person to complement the team and provide the missing area of expertise.

6.5 MONITORING AND EVALUATION

The monitoring and evaluation activities are led by AIT, the partner responsible for the project's impact assessment. AIT has developed a comprehensive framework outlining how this

assessment should be conducted. However, from a methodological perspective, it is necessary to specify the corresponding tasks and highlight the significant contributions of both CSCP, responsible for coordinating the implementation, and SFC, responsible for tracking the effectiveness of the methodology.

- **Training and capacity-building sessions:** AIT will deliver a dedicated training session for the CSLs to explain the impact assessment process, the type of data required, and how it will be collected to ensure an efficient and well-structured evaluation. The session will also clarify the procedures for information transfer between partners. A similar session will be organised for the other project partners to ensure alignment and coherence in the implementation of the impact assessment activities.
- **Impact Board:** CSCP will establish an Impact Board to facilitate the efficient flow of information and data between AIT and the CSLs. This structure will ensure that relevant evidence collected at the local level is systematically transferred, supporting AIT's work in conducting a robust and comprehensive impact assessment.
- **Formative evaluation activities:** These activities aim to provide real-time feedback on CSL performance in relation to the intended impact pathways. They will be conducted in close collaboration with CSCP and SFC. Such meetings offer an opportunity to exchange information and generate actionable insights for CSL Coordinators, implementation coordinators, and the methodological lead, enabling them to adjust and optimise their approaches throughout the project in an iterative manner.

7 CONCLUSION

The methodological framework presented in this document establishes a **coherent, robust and adaptable foundation for the implementation of the SPOON CSLs**. It connects the project's objectives, activities, and expected outcomes through a participatory and evidence-based approach that integrates CS, behavioural insights, and digital innovation. The framework ensures methodological consistency across all CSLs while allowing flexibility for local adaptation, thus fostering both comparability and contextual relevance.

Its successful implementation relies on the active engagement and collaboration of all project partners, particularly CSL coordinators, who play a key role in translating the methodology into practice, and CSCP, who will coordinate the whole implementation with the support of SFC. As an evolving framework, it will remain responsive to the lessons learned throughout the project, continuously integrating feedback from participants, coordinators, and research partners to strengthen SPOON's capacity to generate robust data, empower citizens, and inform the design of effective BCIs.

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